

MODE I FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF THE CFRP ADHESIVE BONDED JOINT UNDER CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURE

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1 Introduction

Application of CFRP to cryogenic propellant tanks can significantly reduce the structural weights of space transportation system. However, cracks often develop in CFRP laminates at cryogenic temperature. These cracks cause a leakage of propellant. In order to prevent the propellant leakage, usually liners are attached to CFRP. Research and development of CFRP cryogenic propellant tank with Al alloy liner was carried out [1]. However, debonding between the CFRP wall and inner Al alloy liner occurred in structural test. Usually, there is large thermal expansion gap between CFRP and liner materials. The temperature difference between curing temperature and environment temperature caused the thermal residual stress and strain, and the debonding occurred on the adhesive. Therefore it is important to investigate fracture toughness of adhesive bonded joint of CFRP laminates and liner for designing CFRP cryogenic tank with the liner. In this study, mode I fracture toughness were measured using DCB tests with three types of bonded specimens. The tests were performed at various temperatures, room temperature, -50°C and cryogenic temperature (-196°C). We must consider effects of residual thermal stress on energy release rate because there is large difference of coefficient of thermal expansion between CFRP and liner material. However, effect of residual thermal stresses is not considered in the standardized test method, such as ASTM. Recently, Yokozeki [3] formulated corrected equations for evaluating energy release rate with residual stresses. In this study, energy release rates with residual stresses were evaluated using Yokozeki's correction method.

2 DCB test

In this study, three types of bonded specimens were tested: CFRP/Adhesive/CFRP (C/C specimen), Aluminum/Adhesive/Aluminum (A/A specimen) and CFRP/Adhesive/Aluminum (C/A specimen). Schematic of specimen is shown in Fig.1. MR50R/#1063EX prepreg (MITSUBISHI RAYON CO., LTD.) was employed for CFRP. Stacking configuration was $[0]_{16}$. MR50R is a PAN based, middle-modulus, high-strength carbon fiber. #1063EX is a toughened epoxy resin. For Aluminum alloy, A6061-T6 was employed. AF163-2K epoxy film adhesive (3M) bonded CFRP layer and Aluminum layer. Glass fiber mesh was used to achieve the uniformity in the adhesive thickness. Aluminum alloy adherends were sanded and anodized using phosphoric acid. The treatment was carried out based on ASTM-D3933. Phosphoric acid anodizing based on ASTM-D3933 was treated with adherent surface of Aluminum alloy. A release film of length of 55mm was placed between CFRP layer and Aluminum. Then, specimen was cured during two hours at 130°C . To install metal jigs in DCB test, there is 20mm length cutout was processed from an end of the specimen. Pre-crack of length of 5mm was introduced into adhesive layer from an end of release film by knocking a wedge at room temperature. DCB test was performed according to JIS (Japan Industrial Standard) K 7086. Experiments were performed under room temperature, -50°C in electric chamber and -196°C in LN₂.

Fig.1 Specimen dimensions

3 Evaluation of energy release rate including residual thermal stress

There is a large difference of thermal expansion coefficient between materials such as CFRP and Al. Therefore, we must consider the effect of residual thermal stress when DCB specimen is subjected to large temperature change. Though DCB test is standardized (e.g. ASTM), the effect of residual stress is not considered. Residual stress is released by crack growth and affects evaluate of energy release rate. According to the ASTM method, the energy is calculated merely from the applied load and crack opening displacements. Thus, energy release rate obtained from experiment is “apparent energy release rate” that does not considered effect of residual stress.

Nairn [2] et.al formulated energy release rate with residual thermal stress. This formulation can be applied to cracked CFRP laminates. Yokozeki [3] et al. formulated energy release rates for a cracked laminates with residual thermal stress. In the present study, to evaluate energy release rate, Yokozeki’s formulation was employed.

Consider a DCB specimen shown in Fig.2. The DCB specimen is divided into three regions. Region 1 is upper beam, Region 2 is lower beam and Region 3 is no-crack-laminate beam. Then, energy release rate with thermal residual stress is given as

$$G_c = G_c^{app} + \frac{P_c \alpha \Delta T}{2B} (F^{(1)} - F^{(2)}) + \frac{(\Delta T)^2}{2B} (I^{(1)} + I^{(2)} - I^{(3)}) \quad (1)$$

where P_c is the applied load, a is the crack length, B is the width of DCB specimen and ΔT is the temperature difference from stress free temperature to experimental temperature. Superscripts (1),(2) and (3) indicate each region shown in Fig.2. In Eq. (1), the first term G_c^{app} is energy release rate without thermal residual stress that is obtained from DCB test. The second term is the coupling term (mechanical load and thermal displacement). The second term corrects the effect of residual thermal displacement at loading point. The third term is the thermal term. We can consider thermal deformation energy release rate by crack growth. By Adding the second and third terms to G_c^{app} , we can evaluate the energy release rate with residual thermal stress. F and I are constants derived

from the classical lamination theory. Those are determined by material constant (Young’s moduli and coefficient of thermal expansion) and the shape of the specimen.

4 Experimental results

Figure 3 shows the relationship between the crack growth and the energy release rate at room temperature. The energy release rates of three specimens were almost the same value. The observation of the crack surface revealed that the cracks grew in the adhesive layer. (see Fig.4).

Fig.2 DCB test specimen

Fig.3 The result of DCB test at room temperature

Fig.4 Fracture interface of specimens at room temperature

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The relationship between crack growth and energy release rate at -50°C was shown in Fig.5. In the case of A/A specimen, the crack grew in the adhesive layer as shown in Fig.6 (a). The energy release rate was almost the same value as the result of room temperature (see Fig.3). We obtained two patterns fracture behavior, adhesive fracture and cohesive fracture, in C/C specimen test at -50°C . In the result of cohesive fracture, energy release rate was not significantly decreased compared with the result of room temperature. On other hand, the result of adhesive failure due to crack deflection was significantly decreased compared with the result of room temperature. Fig.6 (b) and (c) show the fracture surfaces of C/C specimens. Fig.6 (a) shows cohesive failure specimen. We can see the adhesive on both side of the interfaces. Fig.6 (c) is adhesive failure specimen. CFRP surface can be observed in Fig.6 (c).

Fig.6 (d) shows fracture surface of C/A specimen. Pre-crack was introduced into adhesive layer, however the crack deflected into the CFRP layer in -50°C DCB test. Diamond shape symbols denote the results of C/A specimen at -50°C in Fig.5. In the tests of C/A specimens, energy release rates were significantly decreased after crack deflection. And that value was almost the same as the interlaminar energy release rate of MR50R/#1063 at -50°C .

Fig.7 shows the relationship between crack growth and the energy release rates at -196°C . The energy release rate of A/A specimen at -196°C was almost the same value as the results at room temperature and -50°C . The crack grew in adhesive layer as shown in Fig.8 (a). The energy release rates of C/C specimen at -196°C were significantly decreased by comparison with those of room temperature. Fracture surfaces of C/C specimen were shown in Fig.8 (b). In Fig.8 (b), CFRP surfaces were seen on both side of fracture surface. The surface observation revealed that the crack repeatedly deflected into one surface from the other shown as in Fig.9. These results implied that the significant decreases of the energy release rates of C/C specimen at -50°C and -196°C caused by the crack deflection.

In the tests of C/A specimens at -196°C , the crack deflection into CFRP adherend occurred at first crack growth. The crack has reached to the edge of specimen at first crack growth. Therefore we could not obtain energy release rates.

Fig.5 The result of DCB test at -50°C

Fig.6 Fracture interface of specimens at -50°C

Fig.7 The result of DCB test at -196°C

Fig.8 Fracture interface of specimens at -196 °C

Fig.9 Side view of crack growth at -196 °C

5 FEM analysis

To reveal the cause of crack deflection at -50 °C and -196 °C, energy release rate around crack tip was calculated using finite element analysis.

5-1 FEM analysis model

Figure 10 shows the overview of the finite element model used in this study. In the FEA, C/C, A/A, and C/A specimens models were used. The model was two dimensional. Specimen dimensions were: 150mm in length, 2.2mm in CFRP layer thickness, 0.2mm in adhesive layer thickness, 3mm in Al alloy layer thickness and 7mm in crack length from the edge of adhesive layer. Furthermore, three types crack tip models were analyzed for each specimen model as shown in Fig.11: 0crack model, 45crack model and 90crack model. Quadrilateral element was employed, and triangle element was used for crack tip in 45crack model. This FEM models were analyzed under 23°C (room temperature), -50°C, -196°C. Loading point was located at 16 mm from the edge of specimen and 10.24N/mm was applied to that point. This applied load was determined by divided experimental load by specimen width. The material properties used in this FEA are described in

Table 1.VCCT (Virtual Crack Closure Technique) was used to evaluate energy release rate around crack tip. The effects of crack angle and temperature change, for energy release rate, were compared.

5-2 FEM analysis results

The relationship between energy release rate $G_{total} = G_I + G_{II}$ and temperature was shown as in Fig.12. In Fig.12, the energy release rate of 0crack model was the highest in three type models at each temperature. Those analytical results mean that crack growth in adhesive layer does not depend on temperature and were consistent with experimental results.

The results of C/C model were shown in Fig.13. The difference between energy release rate of 45crack and 0crack models decreased as temperature dropped. the decrease was caused by thhe large difference of the coefficient of thermal expansion between the CFRP and the adhesive. The analytical results imply that the difference caused the crack deflection observed in the experiments (see Figs.6(c) and 8(b))

Fig.14 shows FEM analysis results of C/A specimen. At room temperature, G_{total} of 0crack model was higher than in other specimens. At -196 °C, however, G_{total} of 0 crack model was lowest value in three specimens. FEA results shown in Fig.14 are consistent with the experimental results such as Fig.6(d) and Fig.8(c).

Fig.10 FEM analysis mode

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(a) 0crack model

(b) 45crack model

(c) 90crack model

Fig.11 crack tip angle

Table 1 Material properties used in analyses

Material	23 °C			
	CFRP	Al alloy	Adhesive	
Young's modulus [GPa]	E_1	159.60	69.79	2.84
	E_2	8.73	-	-
Shear modulus [GPa]	G_{12}	4.51	-	-
	G_{23}	3.16	-	-
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0.328	0.33	0.32
	ν_{23}	0.381	-	-
Coefficient of thermal expansion [$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$] (30 °C)	a_{11}	-0.02	21.9	37.9
	a_{22}	39.2	-	-
-196 °C				
Material	CFRP	Al alloy	Adhesive	
	CFRP	Al alloy	Adhesive	
Young's modulus [GPa]	E_1	161.30	77.12	9.65
	E_2	12.66	-	-
Shear modulus [GPa]	G_{12}	7.18	-	-
	G_{23}	4.58	-	-
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0.354	0.35	0.44
	ν_{23}	0.381	-	-
Coefficient of thermal expansion [$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$] (-170 °C)	a_{11}	-0.08	17.6	24.3
	a_{22}	30.0	-	-

Fig.12 FEM analysis result: A/A specimen

Fig.13 FEM analysis result: C/C specimen

Fig.14 FEM analysis result: C/A specimen

6 Conclusion

In this study, in order to investigate mode I fracture behavior of the CFRP adhesive bonded joint, DCB test was performed at various temperatures (room temperature, $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and cryogenic temperature).

- At room temperature, Crack extended in the adhesive film and fracture toughness did not depend on the adherend materials.
- In the result of C/C specimen at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and cryogenic temperature, crack was deflected to interface between CFRP and adhesive film, and fracture toughness significantly degraded. On the other hand, fracture toughness of A/A specimen at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and cryogenic temperature were comparable with those at room temperature.
- Fracture toughnesses of C/A specimens were comparable with those of C/C and C/A specimens at room temperature. However, fracture toughness degraded drastically at low and cryogenic temperature.
- FEM analysis was performed to calculate energy release rate around crack tip. FEM results indicated that crack deflections of C/C and C/A specimen were caused by the residual thermal stress.

Reference

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